

Perceived Influence of Educational Planning on Secondary School Goals Delivery in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State

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Abstract

The study investigated the perceived influence of educational planning on secondary school goals delivery in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State. Three objectives, three research questions and three hypotheses guided the study. The study adopted descriptive survey research design. The population of the study was 105 principals (68 males and 37 females) in 35 public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis which consisted of Port Harcourt and Obio/Akpor Local Government Areas in Rivers State. The sample size of the study was 105 principals. The entire 105 principals were study as census without sampling. The instrument for the study was a self-designed questionnaire titled; "Perceived Influence of Educational Planning on Secondary School Goals Delivery Questionnaire. The content and face validity were ascertained by three experts. The reliability of the instrument was determined using Cronbach Alpha method. Reliability indexes of 0.87, 0.76 and 0.93 were obtained for the various clusters of the instrument. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions while z-test statistics was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study revealed that administrative planning, academic planning and co-curricular planning influenced secondary school goals delivery in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State to a high extent. Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended among others that government should develop clear policies that emphasize the integration of co-curricular activities into the educational curriculum.

Keyword: Educational Planning, Administration, Goal Attainment, Co-Curricular Planning

INTRODUCTION

Education involves the process of training a person to develop in him/her good qualities in order to bring out the best in the person. It is the act of training or teaching an individual to learn and acquire desirable skills, attitude, knowledge, values and understanding that will enable the person to think critically about the various issues in life which involve the process of teaching and learning (Olubor, 2014). The learner is taught to understand the deeper things of life, the need for good human relation and the cause-and-effect relationship in life. Education can also be viewed as any act or experience that has a formative effect on the mind, character or physical ability of an individual. It is the process by which a society deliberately transmits its accumulated knowledge, skills and values from one generation to another (Udoh & Akpa, 2017).

According to Froebel cited in Peerzada (2016), education is the unfolding of what is already enfolded in the man. This implies that education is a process through which a person is trained to develop his innate potentials so that it can be fully expressed externally. It is the gradual or progressive development of a person's innate powers or

potentials, which can also be said to be the development from within the individual until the person becomes conscious of his unique existence and begins to seek his own place in society (Peerzada, 2016).

Education is regarded as the key to the development of any nation. It is the tool for a country's political, economic, social and technological development. If education must play its key role in the transformation of nations, it needs to be adequately and effectively planned because a faulty educational planning can jeopardize the development of a nation for decades (Undie, Ekere & Adah, 2017). Planning means deciding in advance what is to be done, when to do it, where to do it, how to do it and who is to do it in order to achieve predetermined goals and objectives.

Planning is fundamental to the achievement of set goals. Planning is a deliberate effort to determine the future course of action for accomplishing predetermined goals and objectives. Akpan (2015) conceptualizes planning as the process of examining the future and drawing up or mapping out a course of action for achieving specified

goals and objectives. It involves working out broad outline the things to be done and procedures for doing them in order to accomplish set purpose. It is a process of making rational and technical choice. Planning is a systematic, conscious and deliberate process of deciding ahead of time, the future course of action that a person wishes to pursue in order to reach set goals. This definition suggests that planning is part and parcel of every man's endeavour politically, socially, economically and academically (Okunamiri, Ibiam & Okunamiri, 2019).

Educational planning involves a systematic and scientific set of decisions for future action with the aim of achieving set educational goals and objectives through effective use of scarce resources. It provides the tool for coordinating and controlling the direction of the educational system so that educational objectives can be realized. It is a process of identifying and classifying educational needs of a nation and the direction education should take and the strategies for implementing decisions concerning educational development (Osareren-Osaghae and Omoike, 2018).

Akpan (2015) maintains that educational planning should reflect the state of development of a nation including the needs and readiness to execute the planned objectives. Thus, educational planning must take into consideration the population growth of children of school age in relation to access to education, educational opportunities and the demand for education.

Combs cited in Akpan, (2015) described educational planning as the application of rational systematic analysis to the process of educational development with the aim of making education more effective and efficient in responding to the needs and goals of the learners and the society. This means that educational planning should take into account the needs of the pupils/students in terms of learning facilities and equipment, textbooks, classroom spaces and qualified educational personnel. In meeting the needs of the society, educational planning should take cognizance of the manpower, cultural, social and communication needs of the society (nation) as well as the economic changes (Akpan, 2015). Therefore, educational planning is a blue-print that gives direction for future development of a nation's educational system and prescribes courses of actions for achieving defined goals and objectives. Educational planning involves

restructuring of the present educational system, forecasting future possibilities, formulating realistic and achievable goals and objectives developing action plans for implementation and periodic appraisal of progress and achievement. The political, social, economic and technological needs of a nation must be considered in educational planning.

Corroborating the afore statement, Beeby cited in Okwori (2018) stated that educational planning is the exercise of foresight in determining the policy, priorities and cost of educational system having due regards for economic and political realities for the system potentials, for growth and for the needs of the country and of the pupils served by the system. This implies that educational planning is a scientific study of the future with regard to a nation's educational development. The future development of a nation is the focus of educational planning. It involves studying the future educational needs of a country and putting in place relevant policies and priorities, actions, and programmes that will enhance achievement of set educational goals. Educational planning does not just happen by chance as it is an organized social practice involving studying the present and using available information concerning the educational challenges of a country to plan for future educational development. The outcome of educational planning is the education plan which contains educational policies, goals and objectives, activities and programmes to be carried out, implementation strategies, method of monitoring and evaluation of achievement and progress and the time frame for implementation (Fadipe, 2016).

Secondary education is the second level in the educational system. The National Policy on Education FRN (2004) asserted that secondary education is the form of education children receive after primary education before the tertiary stage. The broad aim of secondary education is to prepare individuals for higher education and also prepare them for useful living within the society they live. Secondary education consists of senior secondary schools and junior secondary schools. Furthermore, the policy on education stressed that, junior secondary school will be both prevocational and academic in nature. It will teach all the basic subjects which will enable the students to acquire further knowledge and develop skills. According to Abubakar in Offem and Oneful (2020), education is a sure pathway

to liberation of the mind and the improvement of socio-economic status of people. They further explained that education and training help individuals to be empowered and escape poverty by providing them with necessary skills and knowledge to raise their output, income and wealth. Secondary education could change student's mind-set, orientation to values and acquisition of relevant skills. One of the broad aims of secondary education according to the national policy on education (FRN, 2014) is to prepare students for useful living within society and higher education, equip students with practical and vocational skills to make them self-reliant, inculcate moral values, discipline and responsible citizenship.

The goals of secondary education in Nigeria are to:(a) Provide an increasing number of primary school pupils with the opportunity for education of a higher quality, irrespective of sex, or social, religious and ethnic background. (b) Diversify its curriculum to cater for the differences in talents opportunities and roles possessed by or open to students after (their secondary school course. (c) Equip students to live effectively in our modern age of science and technology. (d) Develop and project Nigerian culture, art and language as well as the world's cultural heritage. (e) Raise generation of people who can think for themselves, respect the views and feelings of others, respect the dignity of labour and appreciate those values specified under our broad national aims and live as good citizens. (f) Foster Nigerian unity with an emphasis on the common ties that unite us in our diversity. (g) Inspire students with a desire for achievement and self-improvement both at school and in later life (Obanya 2019). If the above goals of secondary education are properly implemented the secondary education level will be a dependable source of manpower supply for specialized skilled production at the tertiary level. This will increase the nation's production and hence the entire economy.

According to Oboegbulem (2014) in every school system, the student is at the center of the teaching and learning activities. Education in form of teaching and learning is needed for the achievement of useful living among students in the society at large. Useful living within the society implies the development and training of students through school programmes to ensure that, they are propelled towards developing their knowledge, skill, and abilities in diverse ways to be

socioeconomically developed and self-reliant. This development involves the intellectual, physical, social, psychological as well as educational needs of students Section 12, sub-section 114 of the National Policy on education FRN (2009 edition) under "Monitoring and maintenance of minimum standards" stated that the reason why the Federal Government set up the various commission boards council is to ensure that the minimum academic standard prescribed by these Federal Education parastatals are not compromised in any way.

Specifically, sub-section 11 clearly specified the goal of the educational system by the bodies to include. (i). Maintaining and improving standard in all academic programmes and institutions. (ii). Ensuring uniform standard and quality control of instructional activities in institutions and similar status. (iii). Ensuring dissemination of information of innovation and progressive educational principles and practices in these institution through publication, workshop, meeting, seminar and conference. (iv). Obtaining information problems and difficulties of lecturers and institution and offer a practical solution to them.

According to Ukeje, Akabogu and Ndu (2016) for the school to successfully achieve all-round development of students, it has to perform a number of students'-oriented functions, which are academic and administrative. The administrator (principal) has to ensure that the institution instructional programmes are planned and executed for the benefit of the student and the society. Similarly, Abenga (2018) outlined some forms of educational planning to include administrative planning, academic or curricular planning, co-curricular planning, instructional planning, and Institutional Planning.

Administrative planning refers to planning in administrative perspective. In the field of education, administrative planning relates to distribution of responsibilities and powers for different levels of education. Under the administrative educational planning, the administrative responsibilities and powers are planned in relation to the level of different educational administrators. This method of planning education makes a detailed plan on structure and organization of education at different levels – primary, secondary, higher secondary, higher – general, technical and professional (Olubor, 2018). This planning prepares duration of an educational programme, organization and

co-ordination of educational programmes, financial allocation or budget for the programme, engagement of educational officials in the programme, and smooth management of the programme, (Babalola, 2019).

Academic or Curricular planning refers to planning for smooth academic transaction of the syllabus course content for any course at any level of education. It encompasses planning for education in relation to the needs and demands of the individual and society (Osareren-Osaghae & Omoike, 2019). Formulation of educational goals, formation of curriculum committee for development of curriculum and selection of appropriate strategies and methods of teaching, planning of content units, planning for evaluation, planning for review of the curriculum, planning for use of library, planning for special provision for the gifted and remedial instruction for slow learners, (Okwori, 2018).

Co-curricular planning is the planning of education necessary for bringing total development of a student in one point and total development of an educational institution or organization in another point. This planning includes planning for student welfare services, planning for sports and games, planning for social activities and programmes, planning for cultural activities and programmes, planning for hobbies etc, (Igbinedion, 2022). In spite of the fact that the future educational needs of a country must be through relevant policies and programme, there seem to be no direction in this area, hence the study examined, “Perceived influence of educational planning on secondary goals delivery in Port Harcourt Metropolis”

Statement of the Problem

Educational planning plays a critical role in ensuring the effective delivery of secondary school goals, particularly in the areas of student achievement, infrastructure development, teacher effectiveness, and overall school management. In Port Harcourt Metropolis, secondary schools face challenges related to inadequate educational planning, which affects their ability to meet expected academic and developmental objectives. Despite government policies aimed at enhancing educational outcomes, issues such as poor resource allocation, lack of strategic planning, and ineffective monitoring mechanisms continue to hinder the realization of school goals (Schmitt-Cerna, Ramirez-Olascuaga, & Frontiers in Education, 2025).

One of the fundamental concerns in educational planning is the mismatch between policy formulation and implementation. Many secondary schools in Port Harcourt operate without comprehensive strategic plans, leading to inconsistencies in curriculum execution, student performance, and teacher productivity. According to Omiyi, Arubuola, and Chilaka (2025), ineffective educational planning has led to inefficiencies in school administration, resulting in overcrowded classrooms, inadequate instructional materials, and insufficient teacher training programs. These deficiencies contribute to the underachievement of secondary school goals, such as improving student retention rates, fostering innovation in teaching methodologies, and ensuring holistic development.

Additionally, the lack of data-driven decision-making in educational planning exacerbates existing challenges. Effective educational planning relies on accurate data collection and analysis to guide policy decisions and resource distribution. However, in many secondary schools, there is a lack of reliable data to inform planning processes, leading to misallocation of resources and inefficiencies in school management (Ngwarati, 2024). This has raised concerns about the sustainability and impact of educational interventions in achieving long-term school goals.

Furthermore, the recent global educational disruptions caused by the COVID-19 pandemic have highlighted the importance of flexible and adaptive educational planning. Many secondary schools in Port Harcourt struggled to transition to remote or blended learning due to inadequate preparedness and limited infrastructure. This has emphasized the need for well-structured planning frameworks that accommodate unforeseen disruptions and promote resilience in the education sector (Luo, Zhan, & Du, 2025).

Given these challenges, there is a growing need to assess the perceived influence of educational planning on the delivery of secondary school goals in Port Harcourt Metropolis. Hence, the need for this study.

Purpose of the Study

This study examined the perceived influence of educational planning on secondary school goals delivery in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State. The specific objectives of the study were to:

1. Ascertain the extent to which administrative planning influence public secondary school goals delivery in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State.
2. Determine the extent to which academic planning, influence public secondary school goals delivery in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State.
3. Find out the extent to which co-curricular planning influence public secondary school goals delivery in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study

1. To what extent does administrative planning influence secondary school goals delivery in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State?
2. To what extent does academic/curricular planning, influence secondary school goals delivery in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State?
3. To what extent does co-curricular planning, influence secondary school goals delivery in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses which were tested at 0.05 level of significance guided the study:

1. There is no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female principals on the extent to which administrative planning influence secondary school goals delivery in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State.
2. There is no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female principals on the extent to which academic/curricular planning, influence secondary school goals delivery in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State.
3. There is no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female principals on the extent to which co-curricular planning, influence secondary school goals delivery in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State.

METHODOLOGY

The research design for the study was a descriptive survey design. The study was carried out in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis which comprises of Port Harcourt and Obio/Akpor Local Government Areas. The population of the study was 105 principals (68 males and 37 female) in 35 public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis which

consist of Port Harcourt and Obio/Akpor Local Government Areas in Rivers State. The sample size of the study was 105 principals. The entire 105 principals were used as the sample size, since the population of principals in Port Harcourt Metropolis was small, hence the researcher used the entire population as the sample size. The major research instrument that was used for the study was the questionnaire. The title of the instrument is: "Perceived Influence of Educational Planning on Secondary School Goals Delivery Questionnaire (PIEPSSGDQ)". The first part of the questionnaire was the demographic data of the respondents. The second part of the questionnaire consisted of items designed to elicit information from respondents in pursuance of the research questions and the hypotheses. The questionnaire had structured questions divided into sections, A, B, C and D. The Likert rating scale was used in drafting the questionnaire for the study. Each item in the cluster was constructed on a 5-point rating scale of Very High Extent (VHE), High Extent (HE), Moderate Extent (ME), Low Extent (LE) and Very Low Extent (VLE) weighted 5, 4, 3, 2 and 1 respectively.

The instrument was validated by three experts two in Educational Management and one in Measurement and Evaluation, Rivers State University. To determine the reliability of the instrument, the researcher administered 30 copies of the questionnaire to a sample size of 30 principals in Abia State secondary schools, who were not part of the sample of the study, but were chosen because they have similar characteristics with the public secondary schools. The completed copies of the questionnaire were analyzed for reliability using Cronbach Alpha of reliability which gave reliability indexes of 0.87, 0.76 and 0.93, which are high enough for acceptability.

The data collected were analyzed using mean (\bar{x}) and standard deviation (SD) to answer the research questions. The criterion mean that was used in scoring the instrument was 3.00 which signified that the respondents Agree to the item (to a High Extent), as items below 3.00 denotes (Low Extent). It was got by summing up the weighted points and dividing by 5. The null hypotheses formulated were tested using z-test statistics at 0.05 level of significance which is a test of difference of mean. The decision rule was to accept the null hypotheses where the calculated z-value was less than critical z-critical value of ± 1.96 , but reject the null

hypotheses where the calculated z-value was greater than critical z-critical value of ± 1.96 .

Research Question. 1: To what extent does administrative planning influence secondary school goals delivery in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State?

RESULTS

Table 1: Mean Ratings of Respondents on the Extent Administrative Planning Influence Secondary School Goals Delivery in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State

S/N	Items	Principals (Male) N= 68		Principals (Female) N= 37		Average Mean	RMK
		\bar{X}_1	Std ₁	\bar{X}_2	Std ₂		
1.	Administrative planning ensures that resources such as funding, materials, and facilities are distributed efficiently.	4.03	0.56	4.11	0.64	4.07	VHE
2.	Administrative planning supports the development and implementation of curricula that are aligned with the National Policy on Education.	4.05	0.92	3.96	0.96	4.01	VHE
3.	It helps in Infrastructural Development.	4.32	1.22	4.35	1.17	4.34	VHE
4.	It helps in identifying staffing needs, such as recruiting qualified teachers and providing ongoing professional development to improve teaching quality.	3.14	0.73	3.17	0.72	3.16	HE
5.	Administrative planning can enhance the delivery of support services such as counselling, special education, and extracurricular activities.	4.50	1.02	4.55	0.97	4.53	VHE
Grand Mean		4.01		4.03		4.02	VHE

Table 1 in response to research question 1 which states to what extent does administrative planning influence secondary school goals delivery in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State had the following opinion scores for both male and female students. Mean scores of the male principals to questionnaire items 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5 were 4.03, 4.05, 4.32, 3.14 and 4.50 with standard deviations of 0.56, 0.92, 1.22, 0.73 and 1.02 while the mean scores of the female principals were 4.11, 3.96, 4.35, 3.17 and 4.55 with standard deviations of 0.64, 0.96, 1.17, 0.72 and 0.97. Furthermore, the mean set

representing the average mean scores for both male and female principals were 4.07, 4.01, 4.34, 3.16 and 4.53; with standard deviation of 0.60, 0.94, 1.19, 0.72 and 1.00 respectively. The readings which were higher than the criterion mean of 3.00 indicated that administrative planning influence secondary school goals delivery in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State.

Research Question 2: To what extent does academic/curricular planning, influence secondary school goals delivery in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State?

Table 2: Mean Ratings of Respondents on the Extent Academic/Curricular Planning, Influence Secondary School Goals Delivery in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State

S/N	Items	Principals (Male) N= 68		Principals (Female) N= 37		Average Mean	RMK
		\bar{X}_1	Std ₁	\bar{X}_2	Std ₂		
6.	Academic/curricular planning ensures that the curriculum meets educational standards and local needs.	3.70	0.88	3.75	0.84	3.73	HE
7.	By incorporating digital tools and resources into the curriculum for teaching and learning.	4.35	1.16	4.41	1.11	4.38	VHE

8.	By emphasizing the development of critical thinking, problem-solving, and other essential skills that students need for success beyond their schooling.	3.68	1.61	3.74	1.48	3.71	HE
9.	By implementing regular assessments to monitor student progress and adapting 21st century teaching methods.	3.57	0.93	3.63	0.90	3.60	HE
10.	By offering a wide range of subjects to cater for diverse student interests and career aspirations.	3.72	0.85	3.77	0.82	3.75	HE
Grand Mean		3.80		3.86		4.56	VHE

Table 2 in response to research question 2 which states to what extent does academic/curricular planning, influence secondary school goals delivery in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State had the following opinion scores for both male and female principals. Mean scores of the male principals to questionnaire items 6, 7, 8, 9 and 10 were 3.70, 4.35, 3.68, 3.57 and 3.72 with standard deviations of 0.88, 1.16, 1.61, 0.93 and 0.85 while the mean scores of the female principals were 3.75, 4.41, 3.74, 3.63 and 3.77 with standard deviation of 0.84, 1.11, 1.48, 0.90 and 0.82. Furthermore, the mean set representing the grand mean scores for both

male and female principals were 3.73, 4.38, 3.71, 3.60 and 3.75; with standard deviation of 0.86, 1.14, 1.54, 0.92 and 0.83 respectively. The readings which were higher than the criterion mean of 3.00 indicated that academic/curricular planning, influence secondary school goals delivery in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State.

Research Question 3: To what extent does Co-curricular planning, influence secondary school goals delivery in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State?

Table 3: Mean Ratings of Respondents on the Extent Co-Curricular Planning, Influence Secondary School Goals Delivery in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State

S/N	Items	Principals (Male) N= 68		Principals (Female) N= 37		Average Mean	RMK
		\bar{X}_1	Std ₁	\bar{X}_2	Std ₂		
11.	Co-curricular planning allows students to explore strengths and talents outside of academics.	3.65	0.89	3.69	0.87	3.67	HE
12.	Co-curricular planning helps students develop stronger time-management and organization skills.	4.19	1.33	4.20	1.29	4.19	HE
13.	Co-curricular planning helps to build confidence and self-esteem for secondary school goals delivery.	3.00	0.68	3.02	0.67	3.01	HE
14.	Co-curricular planning gives students the opportunity to build friendships and participate in group activities outside of the tight circle of the regular classroom.	3.07	0.78	3.09	0.78	3.08	HE
15.	Co-curricular planning build skills that are not necessarily taught in the classroom but are still important for the future.	3.00	0.75	3.03	0.74	3.02	HE
Grand Mean		3.38		3.41		3.39	HE

Table 3 in response to research question 3 which states to what extent does co-curricular planning, influence secondary school goals delivery in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State had the following opinion scores for both male and female principals. Mean scores of the male principals to questionnaire items 11, 12, 13, 14 and 15 were 3.65,

4.19, 3.00, 3.07 and 3.00 with standard deviations of 0.89, 1.33, 0.68, 0.78 and 0.75 while the mean scores of the female principals were 3.69, 4.20, 3.02, 3.09 and 3.03 with standard deviation of 0.87, 1.29, 0.67, 0.78 and 0.74. Furthermore, the mean set representing the average mean scores for both male and female principals were 3.67, 4.19, 3.01, 3.08

and 3.02; with standard deviation of 0.88, 1.31, 0.68, 0.79 and 0.75 respectively. The readings which were higher than the criterion mean of 3.00 indicated that Co-curricular planning, influence secondary school goals delivery in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State.

Test of Hypotheses

Ho₁: There is no significant difference between the mean responses of male and female principals on the extent administrative planning influence secondary school goals delivery in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State.

Table 4: Z-test Analysis on the Extent Administrative Planning Influence Secondary School Goals Delivery in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State.

Respondents	N	\bar{x}	Std	DF	z-cal	z-crit	LS	Decision
Male Principals	68	4.01	0.89	103	0.99	±1.96	0.05	Ho ₁ Failed to Reject
Female Principals	37	4.03	0.89					No significant difference

Table 4 above shows z-test Analysis on the extent administrative planning influence secondary school goals delivery in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State. The result on the table showed that there is no significant difference between the mean opinion scores of male and female principals on the extent administrative planning influence secondary school goals delivery in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State. The result on the table further showed a z-calculated value of 0.99 which was less than the z-critical value of ±1.96 at 0.05 level of significance and with a degree of freedom of 103, since the z-calculated (0.99) was less than the z-

tabulated (±1.96). The null hypothesis was therefore accepted which states that there is no significant difference between the mean opinion scores of male and female principals on the extent administrative planning influence secondary school goals delivery in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State.

Ho₂: There is no significant difference between the mean responses of male and female principals on the extent academic/curricular planning, influence secondary school goals delivery in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State.

Table 5: Z-test Analysis on the Extent Academic/Curricular Planning, Influence Secondary School Goals Delivery in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State.

Respondents	N	\bar{x}	Std	DF	z-cal	z-crit	LS	Decision
Male Principals	68	3.80	1.17	103	0.36	±1.96	0.05	Ho ₂ Failed to Reject
Female Principals	37	3.86	1.03					No significant difference

Table 5 above shows z-test Analysis on the extent academic/curricular planning, influence secondary school goals delivery in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State. The result on the table showed that there is no significant difference between the mean opinion scores of male and female principals on the extent academic/curricular planning, influence secondary school goals delivery in Port Harcourt Metropolis of

Rivers State. The result on the table further showed a z-calculated value of 0.36 which was less than the z-critical value of ±1.96 at 0.05 level of significance and with a degree of freedom of 103, since the z-calculated (0.36) was less than the z-tabulated (±1.96). The null hypothesis was therefore accepted which states that there is no significant difference between the mean opinion scores of male and female principals on the extent

academic/curricular planning, influence secondary school goals delivery in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State.

H₀₃: There is no significant difference between the mean responses of male and female principals on the extent Co-curricular planning, influence secondary school goals delivery in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State.

Table 6: Z-test Analysis on the Extent Co-Curricular Planning, Influence Secondary School Goals Delivery in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State.

Respondents	N	\bar{x}	Std	DF	z-cal	z-crit	LS	Decision
Male Principals	68	3.38	0.89	103	0.73	±1.96	0.05	H ₀₃ Failed to Reject No significant difference
Female Principals	37	3.41	0.87					

The result on Table 6 above shows z-test Analysis on the extent Co-curricular planning, influence secondary school goals delivery in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State. The result on the table showed that there is no significant difference between the mean opinion scores of male and female principals on the extent Co-curricular planning, influence secondary school goals delivery in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State. The result on the table further showed a z-calculated value of 0.73 which was less than the z-critical value of ±1.96 at 0.05 level of significance and with a degree of freedom of 103, since the z-calculated (0.73) was less than the z-tabulated (±1.96). The null hypothesis was therefore accepted which states that there is no significant difference between the mean opinion scores of male and female principals on the extent Co-curricular planning, influence secondary school goals delivery in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of the study for research question 1 revealed that male and female principals to a very high extent agreed that administrative planning ensures that resources such as funding, materials, and facilities are distributed efficiently. Administrative planning supports the development and implementation of curricula that are aligned with the National Policy on Education. It helps in Infrastructural Development. It helps in identifying staffing needs, such as recruiting qualified teachers and providing ongoing professional development to improve teaching quality. Administrative planning can enhance the delivery of support services such as counselling, special education, and extracurricular activities. The grand mean for both

male and female principals was 4.02 indicating that administrative planning influence secondary school goals delivery in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State. The study was supported by the findings of Kithandiand Shuna (2024) found that effective administrative planning enhances school performance by ensuring proper resource allocation, staff management, and operational efficiency. Their study emphasized that well-structured planning reduces disruptions and improves goal achievement in secondary education.

The result of hypothesis 1 showed a z-calculated value of 0.99 while the z-critical value was ±1.96, at 103 degree of freedom. It was thus established that since the z-calculated was less than the z-critical value, the null hypothesis 1 was accepted which states that there is no significant difference between the mean opinion scores of male and female principals on the extent administrative planning influence secondary school goals delivery in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State. This is in consonance with the findings of Schmitt-Cerna, Ramirez-Olascuaga and Frontiers in Education (2025) highlighted that administrative leadership plays a vital role in creating a structured learning environment. They found that schools with well-defined administrative strategies reported higher student engagement and academic success.

The finding of the study for research question 2 revealed that male and female principals to a high extent agreed on all the items 6, 7,8, 9 and 10. The table 4.2 showed that the grand rating mean for male respondents is 3.80 with a standard deviation of 1.17 while that of female respondents are 3.86 and 1.03 as their standard deviation. These grand mean values are above the criterion mean of

3.00 which suggest that academic planning influence secondary school goals delivery. This result is in consonance with the findings of Sapry and Jameel (2024) who found that schools with well-organized academic planning frameworks achieved better student performance, particularly in STEM subjects. Their research highlighted that strategic curriculum design improves learning outcomes.

The result of hypothesis 2 indicated a z-calculated value of 0.36, while the z-critical was ± 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance with a degree of freedom of 103. Since the z-calculated was less than the z-critical of ± 1.96 , the null hypothesis was accepted which states that there is no significant difference between the mean opinion score of male and female principals on the extent academic planning influence secondary school goals delivery in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State. This is further supported by the findings of Ismanto and Trisatyawati (2024) who emphasized that academic planning, including teacher training programs and lesson structuring, enhances instructional quality and student retention rates in secondary schools.

The finding of the study for research question 3 revealed that all the respondents agreed on all the items with a grand mean of 3.38 and a standard deviation of 0.89 for male respondents while females had 3.41 as grand mean response and 0.87 as standard deviation. The grand mean scores were above the criterion mean of 3.00. This infers that all the respondents agreed that co-curricular planning influence secondary school goals delivery. It also depicted that co-curricular planning has positive influence on secondary school goals delivery in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State to a great extent. The findings of the study agree with Igbinedion (2022), who stated that co-curricular planning is necessary for bringing total development of a student in one point and total development of an educational institution.

Result displayed on table 6 was used to test hypothesis 3 at 0.05 level of significance. The result indicates a z-calculated value of 0.73 while the z-critical is ± 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance and at 103 degree of freedom. Since the z-calculated value of 0.73 was less than the z-critical value of ± 1.96 , the null hypothesis 3 which states that there is no significant difference in the mean opinion scores of male and female principals on the extent co-curricular planning influence secondary school goals delivery in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State was

accepted. This study is supported by the findings of Bullinger and Shi (2025) which revealed that schools with well-structured co-curricular programs experienced increased student participation, better social skills development, and improved academic performance. Similarly, Mutswenje (2024) found out that co-curricular activities such as sports, debates, and leadership training enhance students' critical thinking and teamwork abilities, contributing to overall school success.

CONCLUSION

In view of the results obtained from the study, the researcher concluded that administrative planning, academic planning and co-curricular planning, to a high extent influence on public senior secondary schools goal delivery in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study the following recommendations were made:

1. The government of Rivers State should in administrative planning develop clear policies for staff recruitment, training and welfare.
2. Principals should in academic/curriculum planning incorporate flexible and students centered teaching methods, and also regularly update subject content to reflect current knowledge and skills demands
3. The government should develop clear policies that emphasize the integration of co-curricular activities into the educational curriculum. School management should develop comprehensive co-curricular plans that align with the school's academic goals and cater to diverse student interests

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